

Inference of Unresolved Point Sources and Cosmic X-ray Background from the Chandra Deep Field - South (CDF-S) Survey using Probabilistic Catalogs

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ABSTRACT

Being able to accurately characterize populations of astrophysical sources from observation is a crucial element of astronomy. From accurate cataloging, one can develop population and background emission statistics that describe how those populations evolve over time. However, given limited photon counts and finite exposure times, precise characterizations are always incomplete, since some sources are too faint relative to background noise. In this paper, we apply a probabilistic catalog method with PCAT, which employs a Bayesian, trans-dimensional Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) simulation. This approach samples from the posterior distribution of all possible catalogs consistent with the observation in order to constrain different parameters of our catalog. Our method is trans-dimensional in the sense that we are able to include the number of sources as a floating parameter, enabling us to explore the population statistics of lower significance sources. In applying PCAT to X-ray data, we model Chandra's Point Spread Function (PSF) which has both an energy and off-axis angle dependence. After testing our method with mock data and exploring our systematics, we present preliminary results of PCAT applied to the Chandra Deep Field - South (CDF-S) survey. The CDF-S dataset is a particularly good target for probabilistic cataloging because of the extremely low number of photon counts collected.

1. Introduction

The study of astrophysical phenomena and cosmic evolution has been significantly enhanced by a wealth of X-ray data coming from the Chandra X-ray Observatory and X-ray Multi-Mirror Mission (XMM-Newton) over the past twenty years. The first discovery of a cosmic X-ray source occurred in 1962, when Riccardo Giacconi observed the compact star

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Scorpius X-1. Since then, a host of X-ray sources have been studied, e.g., neutron stars, active galactic nuclei (AGN), supernova remnants, etc. X-ray emission is generally associated with extremely hot gases at temperatures of order $10^6 - 10^8$ Kelvin, and thus provides an invaluable window into galactic and cosmic evolution.

In particular, ultra-deep X-ray surveys allow the analysis of X-ray sources at high redshifts, probing fainter objects from larger distances. The Chandra Deep Field - South (CDF-S) survey is a prime example of this, largely by nature of being the deepest X-ray survey to date. The CDF-S survey covers a field of view of 465 square arcminutes and, as of this year, has a total exposure of 7 Ms (Luo et al. 2017, referred to as L17 from here on). CDF-S now has the depth required to study objects at redshifts as high as $z = 5$, corresponding to objects formed during the first Gyr of the universe. This, combined with a high angular resolution for near-axis sources, makes CDF-S an extremely valuable survey.

Being able to characterize the cosmic X-ray background (CXB) is crucial in understanding early universe history, like the formation of normal and starburst galaxies, or the coevolution of SMBHs with galaxies in the era $z \sim 1 - 4$. In their most recent paper on the 7 Ms CDF-S data set, L17 were able to resolve $80.9\% \pm 4.4\%$ and $92.7\% \pm 13.3\%$ of the CXB into AGN and other sources, for the soft (0.5-2 keV) and hard (2-7 keV) X-ray bands, respectively. This improvement on previous 4 Ms CDF-S resolved fractions of $75.7\% \pm 4.3\%$ in the soft band and $82.4\% \pm 13.0\%$ in the hard band is expected, since more observing time means sources near lower flux limits become identifiable. Nonetheless, there is still work to be done in characterizing the remaining unresolved CXB. Some of this background may come from the Local Bubble (Galeazzi et al. 2014), and a considerable amount comes from instrumental background – in fact, Hickox and Markevitch 2006 demonstrates that the quiescent instrumental background is ~ 5 and ~ 25 larger than the unresolved sky signal for the soft and hard bands, respectively. Aside from these sources though, it is unclear whether the remaining CXB is comprised of dimmer point sources, or possibly a true diffuse background. Moving forward, it is crucial to understand these different components and be able to track their uncertainties. In this paper, we approach the problem by employing a probabilistic, Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) catalog, which samples all catalogs consistent with the data to provide robust uncertainties on the various parameters of our catalog and background model. This approach should ultimately provide better constraints the CXB than ever before.

The structure of this paper is the following. In Section 2 we describe the probabilistic cataloguing approach and its advantages over traditional cataloguing techniques. Section 3 discusses CDF-S and the creation of models for various components of the data. In Section 4, we apply our approach to mock generated data, followed by Section 5 in which we apply

the method to a small central region of CDF-S 4 Ms data. Section 6 includes a discussion of our results and plans for future investigation, and in Section 7 we provide a summary of our main results.

2. Probabilistic Cataloguing

In astronomy, the inference of point sources is accompanied by a host of difficulties. Due to finite exposures and limited photon counts, observations contain noise that prevents definitive detection of fainter sources. This does, by nature, play a part in most astronomical observations. However, the effects on X-ray data cannot be understated; as one can see in Figure 1, the median number of photon counts per pixel in the CDF-S 7 Ms survey is zero. Thus, in the extreme Poissonian limit, it becomes difficult to detect sources at high confidence levels. If one imposes a hard detection limit of 5σ , as most catalogs do, then many fainter sources ($2\sigma - 4\sigma$) are absorbed into the diffuse background rather than detected. This both inaccurately characterizes the CXB and yields inaccurate flux distribution functions at the dim end. The conventional method to cataloging sources is deterministic. Here, one asks what specific catalog maximizes the likelihood that our observation is generated by the model. Our model, the catalog, is defined by the set of source positions, fluxes, and colors. However, just because a catalog maximizes a prescribed likelihood function, it does not mean it most closely resembles the true catalog, i.e. the real distribution of astrophysical sources that exists in a given field of view. One can imagine a situation in which two adjacent sources are blended together in the maximum likelihood catalog, or conversely, photons coming in from one source might be deemed two separate sources. Background noise fluctuations might also produce a spurious source in the maximum likelihood catalog. Because the deterministic cataloging approach produces one realization of the catalog, it is unable to track uncertainties associated with these types of corner cases, nor with faint sources that might appear just below the detection significance threshold.

These reasons have led some groups to adopt a probabilistic approach in the task of point source inference. Developed initially by Brewer et al. (2012) in application to crowded stellar fields, the probabilistic approach places Bayesian priors on parameters within a given model, but also generates multiple models that have a number of point sources between N_{min} and N_{max} . Through Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), one can sample both within and across models for different numbers of sources and, given a sufficient number of steps in the total parameter space, converge on a stationary distribution for the relevant parameters. In effect, the probabilistic approach samples from the many different realizations of catalogs consistent with a given image. From here, one might take the most likely configuration in

the posterior distribution and denote that as their "catalog". However, astronomers are oftentimes more concerned with population statistics as a whole – this approach enables one to characterize and track uncertainties from the many realizations of the source population. In the context of this project, we want to track the number of sources, the flux distribution, and the color distribution (in X-ray astronomy, "color" refers to the flux ratio of the soft X-ray (0.5-2 keV) and hard X-ray (2-7 keV) bands). This information, in turn, gives information on the resolved/unresolved CXB.

2.1. MCMC Sampling Method

Here we describe the Markov Chain Monte Carlo sampling method used in this project. The method is described in further detail in Daylan et al. 2016, though we make some important modifications in applying PCAT specifically to X-ray data. For consistency, we use the same notation as in the paper mentioned above.

Let the catalog space we sample from be denoted \mathcal{C} . This catalog space is the union of $N_{max} - N_{min}$ sub-catalog spaces, where each sub-catalog represents a model with some specified number of point sources N . For each point source, we want to model the longitude and latitude, (l, b) , the flux, f , and color, s . Thus the full catalog space can be represented as

$$\mathcal{C} = \bigcup_{N=N_{min}}^{N_{max}} \mathcal{L}_N \times \mathcal{B}_N \times \mathcal{F}_N \times \mathcal{S}_N \quad (1)$$

To obtain a posterior stationary distribution, one needs to construct a Markov chain of states x , which are then updated via Bayes' law

$$P(x | D) \propto P(x)P(D | x) \quad (2)$$

In this equation, $P(x)$ represents our prior for x and $P(D | x)$ represents the likelihood of observing data D given the model. The MCMC approach follows a specific algorithm that is proven to converge on a stationary distribution. First, one defines priors beliefs for parameters x_0 of a given model. Next, for each iteration t , a candidate x' is generated from some predefined probability distribution function $g(x' | x_t)$. The proposed step from x_t to x' is accepted with acceptance probability

$$\alpha(x' | x_t) = \min \left(1, \frac{P(x' | D)}{P(x | D)} \right) \quad (3)$$

Because we wish to iterate this process over our parameters to reach a stationary distribution, the Markov chain we construct must be reversible. That is, given a pair of states

x and x' , the probability of being in state x and transitioning to x' must be equal to being in x' and transitioning to x . This condition is also referred to as detailed balance.

One crucial element of the PCAT method concerns the trans-dimensional nature of the catalog space. If one wants to add or remove a source from a catalog, four parameters need to be added or removed from the model, namely the 2D position, flux, and color of the source. Each source has these four parameters, so models that differ by n sources also differ in dimension by $4n$. When trying to jump across models of different dimension, this transition cannot be one-to-one, thus breaking the reversibility condition. This issue is resolved by drawing random dummy variables u and u' with densities $g(u)$ and $g(u')$ to match the dimensions of the initial and final states, where

$$\mathcal{D}(x) + \mathcal{D}(u) = \mathcal{D}(x') + \mathcal{D}(u') \quad (4)$$

and \mathcal{D} is the dimension operator. These extra variables allow detailed balance to be preserved without biasing the final stationary distribution.

From the assumption that each point source in our model is independently realized and are not spatially or spectrally correlated with other sources, one can construct a hierarchical Bayesian model. In the hierarchical model, every point source has priors on its parameters (e.g. flux, color), which are then parametrized by hyper-parameters which float in the fit. For example, we characterize our population’s flux distribution by the hyper-parameter α , which represents the power-law slope of the distribution. This, of course, requires one to adopt the prior belief (this is technically a hyperprior of the whole model) that the flux distribution follows a power law in the first place, which adds another level to model – this is precisely what makes the model hierarchical. For the purposes of this project, we adopt a power-law hyperprior on source fluxes and a Gaussian hyperprior on source colors.

It should also be noted that the Chandra Point Spread Function (PSF), while not hierarchical in this context, is another crucial part of our model as a whole. We seek to parametrize the PSF as a Gaussian, which then has its own dependencies and assumptions which we will discuss in section 3.

3. Chandra Deep Field - South Survey

In this section we describe the main features of CDF-S and the specific models used in PCAT. CDF-S was completed over a series of observing periods. The first 2Ms exposure was done between October 15 1999 and November 4 2007, the next 2Ms between March 18 2010 and July 22 2010, and the final 3Ms between 2014 and 2016. This totals to 102 individual observations, each done with ACIS-I CCDs on Chandra. The merged 4 Ms and 7

Fig. 1.—: Maps of the Chandra Deep Field - South Survey. Full band image (left) and effective exposure (right). Note that the exposure map

Ms data used in this paper were obtained from <http://www2.astro.psu.edu/~niel/cdfs/cdfs-chandra.html>, where full data products and research papers related to CDF-S data is posted. Though we did not process this data ourselves, it has been reduced, according to L17, with standard Chandra X-ray Center (CXC) pipeline software. Level 1 files are reprocessed with ACIS PROCESS EVENTS, which applies Charge Transfer Inefficiency (CTI) corrections and flags potential cosmic-ray background events for Very Faint mode data. L17 implemented a custom stripped-down bad-pixel file different from the standard CXC one in order to recover good events lost in the standard bad-pixel file method. There are other modifications made on the standard CXC pipeline in producing the data used here – this can be found in L17, §2.2. As can be seen in Figure 1, the merged image of CDF-S has a staggered pattern. This happens because Chandra does not maintain the same pointing direction across exposures, but instead dithers in the shape of a Lissajous figure.¹ By doing this, Chandra averages over any calibration uncertainties, keeps individual bad pixels from ruining observations, and smooths out the gaps between ACIS chips. The orthogonal gaps between CCDs can be seen fairly clearly in the combined exposure map for CDF-S (Figure 1, right).

The data is separated into soft (0.5-2 keV) and hard (2-7 keV) X-ray band components. To fully model the observations, we need to account for the different types of background. First, there is a cosmic-ray component coming from high energy particles hitting the de-

¹<http://www-gap.dcs.st-and.ac.uk/history/Curves/Lissajous.html>

tectors: the published CDF-S data is already processed to some extent, with cosmic-ray afterglow events and overheated pixels already removed. Second, there is a quiescent particle background that comes from interactions within the detector and fluorescent X-ray emission from particle interaction with the detector and surroundings. For this project, we use an isotropic background in our mock data run and do not attempt to separate our non-source background into multiple components. However, Chandra’s ”stowed” background provides an excellent opportunity to do so in the near future. For the stowed background, the ACIS detector is obscured from the sky background, and in 2006 Hickox et al. showed that the stowed background is representative of the quiescent sky particle background by comparing it to observations of the dark Moon and finding that the two are spectrally identical and time-independent ⁴. The stowed background is, however, spatially nonuniform; we will eventually use the analytical model derived in Bartalucci et al. 2014. This instrumental particle background is modeled from ACIS-stowed data from observing periods D + E in Very Faint (VF) mode to a 2 percent level of precision. Even with these various forms of background, we are dealing with very few photons, as is demonstrated in Figure 2.

After removing these forms of background, we are left with the true CXB, which we want to characterize into resolved point sources and unresolved diffuse background. L17 create a background map by masking out the catalog-identified sources at some sufficient radius, and then filling in the masked regions with random counts consistent with the local background level. This is problematic for the same reasons as described earlier; sources with detection limits slightly below the detection threshold established become part of the background counts that are then used to generate appropriate background count levels for the masked regions. By floating the number of sources in our method, we are also effectively floating the background levels, such that possible contributions from lower significance sources get factored into the background stationary distribution.

Fig. 2.—: Histograms for individual photon counts, given in the soft, hard, and full X-ray bands. The Poissonian statistical limit is particularly relevant for this level of photon counts, though not all elements of the observed photon count map are Poissonian in nature. For non-zero pixels, the hard X-ray band contains the majority of photon counts.

⁴The quiescent particle background does actually have some minor time dependence, with fluctuations at the $\sim 10\%$ level over time scales corresponding to solar cycles.

3.1. Parametrizing the Chandra Point Spread Function

It is crucial that we parametrize the Chandra Point Spread Function (PSF) in both energy bands for our model. Unlike most telescopes, the PSF for Chandra is highly variable, depending on the energy and distance from the optical axis (off-axis angle from here on out) on the detector. We model the PSF approximately as a Gaussian of the form $\exp(-\frac{\theta^2}{2*\sigma^2}) = \exp(-\frac{4\ln 2\theta^2}{f^2})$ where f is the full width half maximum (FWHM) of the Gaussian. There is no direct analytic expression for the FWHM as a function of energy and off-axis angle, leading us to compute a best fit to given data. It should also be noted that the Chandra PSF becomes more elliptical with increasing off axis angle, with an ellipticity of ~ 0.4 at an off axis angle of 5 arcminutes (Allen et al. 2003). However, because the region of CDF-S that we analyze in this paper is only ~ 1 arcmin in radius, our full PSF size goes up to ~ 1 arcsecond. This translates to a length of two pixels, which is why we feel justified in approximating our PSF as radially symmetric. For applications of PCAT to larger ROIs in the future, however, it may be necessary to model the PSF as an ellipsoid with azimuthal dependence. At small off axis angles, the extended tail of Chandra PSF is also less important, but bright sources in the ROI do help to constrain these tails in any circumstance; otherwise they become degenerate with the unresolved background.

Using the Chandra PSF Viewer ², we generate data giving the 50 percent Enclosed Counts Fraction (ECF) radii for different values in the energy/off-axis angle parameter space. The 50 percent ECF is equal to $f/2$. We then fit the data with a 2D, third degree polynomial by implementing a Levenberg-Marquardt least-squares minimization, which is shown in Figure 3 (left). We want a FWHM fit for each of the two bands, so we evaluate this 2D fit at the geometric means of each band, i.e. $E_{soft} = \sqrt{0.5 * 2} = 1\text{keV}$ and $E_{hard} = \sqrt{2 * 7} = 3.7\text{keV}$.

Finally, we model each energy bin's off-axis angle dependence with a pivoted power law given by

$$f(\theta, E_{fixed}) = f(0, E_{fixed}) + a(\theta/3')^b \quad (5)$$

We then do another least squares minimization to obtain values for a and b , which are displayed in Table 1.

Modeling the PSF is crucial in generating an accurate model of the observed photon count map, since observed sources are the result of convolutions between true point sources, described by delta functions, with corresponding PSFs. When calculating fluxes, then, it is necessary to reverse this process, de-convolving the observed source for a region prescribed

²<http://cxc.harvard.edu/cgi-bin/prop-viewer/build-viewer>

Fig. 3.—: 2D best fit polynomial for 50% ECF of Chandra PSF (left). As one can see, the FWHM increases with off-axis angle as well as energy. The mean relative error for our 2D fit is calculated to be $\sigma_{rel} = 0.168$. We ultimately split into two energy bins and calculate the best fit pivoted power law for each (right). One can see that variation between FWHM for the soft and hard bands is subtle.

Table 1:: Best-fit FWHM Parameters

	Soft Band	Hard Band
a	2.19462	1.01664
b	1.96858	2.12966

by our PSF. The PSF FWHM parameters are part of the parameter space sampled by our PCAT, which ultimately provides constraints on these parameters as well. We derive best fit parameter values in Table 1 as informed priors for our MCMC, and are constrained (loosely) to $\pm 16.8\%$ as described in Figure 3.

4. Mock Data

In this section we present results from the application of PCAT to simulated mock X-ray data. This mock data is a Poisson realization of emission due to point-sources and a diffuse background. we generate 50 point sources from a predefined flux distribution with a given power law slope of based on prior Chandra data. We do a mock run in order to compare our MCMC results with definite population characteristics, whereas we do not know the true characteristics of true observed data.

Our MCMC run on the mock data is done with 500000 steps, with the first 50000 steps

discarded as "burn-in", the period in which our Markov chains are exploring the parameter space broadly before they converge on the stationary distribution. The burn in portion of the Markov chain is not representative of the stationary distribution, and so we do not want to incorporate it when we evaluate our total chain. After removing this portion of each chain, and then split the resulting chain into 450 separate chains. Since our MCMC run involves a large number of parameters and is fairly expensive computationally, it may be unclear at what point the chain converges, i.e. when we have taken a sufficient number of steps. By splitting up our chain, we can evaluate the Gelman-Rubin statistic utilized in Daylan et al. 2016,

$$R = \sqrt{1 + \frac{B}{W} - \frac{1}{N_s}} \tag{6}$$

In the above equation, B is the between-chain variance, i.e. the variance of the chain means, W is the within-chain variance, i.e., the mean of the chain variances, and N_s is the number of samples in each chain. This should be close to unity if the chains have converged.³

We can also test the memory-less property of our Markov chain by computing the auto-correlation of our split chains. If the auto-correlation converges to 0 then we can confirm a stationary distribution has been reached. Figure 4 shows the auto-correlation for our chain – the timescale for convergence is characterized by τ_{exp} , which appears to be less than the timescale of our full MCMC run.

Individual samples of our MCMC are shown in Figure 5, where we plot maps of the mock map, the sampled model map, and the residuals. The mock and sampled model maps are over-plotted with different stars, pluses, and circles, which indicate at which positions the model has "found" a point source in the data. Because we are working with mock data, it is a good reality check to see if our model matches the mock data. The maps shown are just one realization from the 500000 samples taken in this run, so some sources that are mock misses in this realization might be mock hits in others, and vice-versa. While it is hard to talk about individual sources within the ROI in a way which is directly

Fig. 4.—: Auto-correlation for MCMC Mock Data Run. This does appear to converge to zero, demonstrating the memoryless property.

³On a more general note, because our model has a source-labeling degeneracy in which the parameter labels of N point sources can be permuted, our likelihood function has an N!-fold degeneracy. This means that while we are looking for maximum of our overall likelihood function, there are actually N! maxima which our sampler could converge on. This fact obscures the notion of formal convergence, but as long we can converge on one likelihood peak we can achieve a stationary distribution.

Fig. 5.—: From left to right: Map of counts from generated mock data, map of counts from model at one sample point, map of residual counts from mock data minus model counts. All maps displayed are in the soft X-ray band. If a mock source is not hit, it is superimposed with a green X. If the source is matched positionally but does not have a matched flux, then it is labeled with a green circle. If both flux and position are matched then the source is labeled with a green star.

informative, one can see that almost all of the sample point sources are mock hits, or mock misses (source matched positionally but not by flux within some margin of error). Our posteriors, which we include later in this section, give further confirmation that our MCMC is converging on the stationary distribution of our parameters.

Fig. 6.—: Marginalized posterior distributions for source fluxes in soft band (left) and color index (right), with error bars representing the marginalized uncertainties at each point.

Figure 6 shows the posteriors for flux and color index compared to the true mock data. Because our MCMC run is done on a small number of mock sources, these distributions are rather discrete, though one can see the overall trend of a power law and Gaussian spread for

flux and color index, respectively. The top horizontal axis of our flux distribution represents the associated number of photon counts. One might note that the majority of sources occur on the faint end, where our sources are comprised of only 4-5 photon counts. This is the regime where PCAT distinguishes itself from other methods, since it is in this regime where population statistics are least understood.

Figure 7 is used to compare the true mock source fluxes with those obtained by PCAT. In this scatter plot, sources are only plotted if their positions are matched by the probabilistic catalog and their fluxes are within the tolerance region outlined by the dashed diagonal lines above and below our sources. Almost all of our sources are included within these tolerances, and this is reflected further by Figure 8a, which shows the posterior on the number of sources estimated by PCAT. We see a median number of sources that is ~ 55 rather than 50, but overall this is pretty close considering many of these sources are dim and our sampler will inevitably sample faint sources that are actually background, since the two become nearly degenerate. This slight excess of sources can also be seen from the perspective of Figure 8b, where the median for our posterior of background normalization is slightly below the true normalization.

Fig. 7.—: Posterior median flux association between the mock and probabilistic catalog for the soft (left) and hard (right) X-ray bands. In a ideal situation with no noise, our sources would fall on the $x = y$ line, but realistically we have uncertainties that prevent this from happening. Marginalized flux uncertainties are also plotted as error bars for individual sources.

Fig. 8.—: Left: Posterior for the number of sources estimated by PCAT during the mock data run. This includes the Markov chain as a function of sample index and associated histogram with the true number of sources marked in green along with 1 and 2 σ margins. Right: Posterior for background normalization, where true normalization is set to unity.

4.1. Mock Data Run on (Effectively) Background Only

In order to understand how many sources our method may be falsely including in the posterior distributions, we also ran PCAT in the case where there is only one source within the same ROI rather than 50⁵ This run is done with the same number of samples as our first mock data run, and as can be seen in Figure 9, PCAT converges on a posterior with a mode of 1 source. There is a tail to the distribution such that the median is closer to 2 sources, but overall this is promising in the context of future estimates on the number of spurious detections made by PCAT.

Fig. 9.—: Posterior for the number of sources estimated by PCAT during mock data run with one source

⁵It should be noted that it would be ideal to run PCAT on a background with no sources at all, but technical difficulties limit our capabilities to this for the meanwhile.

5. CDF-S 7 Ms Data

In this section, we present preliminary results of PCAT applied to a region of CDF-S. For now, we limit our ROI to an area of 1 square arcminute centered on axis. Future work will use a larger ROI, but at this point in the process, 1 square arcminute is sufficient. In our model, we also assume that background is isotropic, though this will certainly change in the near future. For this region we run PCAT with 2000000 steps, discarding the first 200000 as burn in. Figure 10 shows the binned posterior of our run, separated into spatial bins and flux bins. By spatial bins, all we are doing is projecting the posterior onto our ROI, such that one can see where sources were identified in the various fair samples. With proper normalization, this map provides an effective probability of finding a source for a given position and flux bin given the model. It makes sense, then, that the posterior is less saturated in higher flux bins, as the number of samples decreases and converges on bright, easily identifiable sources in the observed image.

Fig. 10.—: Posterior distribution binned spatially and by flux.

The posterior distributions for our PSF parameters is given in Figure 11a (left). We let the FWHM float in this MCMC run, which in turn means we are floating a and b with

priors from §3.1. In this corner plot, we can examine both the marginalized posteriors for our parameters (σ , a , b), as well as each of the 2D posteriors between parameters. While there is a slightly negative covariance between b and σ , our posteriors are largely Gaussian, which is a good indication that we have approached a stationary distribution. With this in mind, Figure 11b is of particular interest. While PCAT calculates a median of ~ 100 sources for our posterior, the most recent catalog by L17 only identifies 11 sources within the same region. This may seem contradictory, when in fact this is actually indicative of PCAT identifying fainter sources within the region. With a flux distribution power law slope of ~ 1.9 , one should actually expect a factor of ~ 10 more sources than the conventional catalog.

6. Future Work with PCAT and CDF-S

While we have presented preliminary results for PCAT applied to CDF-S, there is a lot of work yet to be done. Our primary objective for the immediate future is to generate a map of effective particle background over the merged CDF-S survey. Once we are able to generate an effective background map for the merged CDF-S map, we will use the analytical model from Bertalucci et al. to represent each individual exposure, from which we can sum up our individual backgrounds in a manner which is consistent with the dithered pattern of CDF-S. We will then be able to compare our model with the catalog we retrieved from L17, checking whether significant sources are matched by both and to what extent PCAT generates stronger uncertainties on background flux and the number of point sources.

One major source of potential error may arise from the PSF if it is not modeled well. This is one of the major sources of uncertainty because of the variability it brings, and so we may look to another parametrization if ours does not fit well for larger ROIs in the future. It is known that for at larger off axis angles, the Chandra PSF has extended tails, and so we may adopt a single King function in place of the single tailed Gaussian. Compared simulations with each will tell us which is more suitable, since the Gaussian PSF has the potential advantage of being just as accurate as a King function with less complexity.

7. Summary

For this project, we applied a probabilistic cataloging approach to X-ray data from the Chandra Deep Field - South Survey. We use a trans-dimensional MCMC approach in order to both infer the properties of given sources along with the number of sources in the

Fig. 11.—: Left: Posterior distributions for Chandra PSF parameters. First column gives posterior for Gaussian width σ , second for normalization factor a , and third for power law slope β for FWHM dependence. Right: Posterior histogram for number of sources identified by PCAT in run on CDF-S data. The median number of sources here is ~ 100 .

given data set. Due to the extremely low number of photon counts associated with X-ray data, we reach an extreme Poisson limit which provides a particularly good opportunity to utilize a probabilistic approach. We first apply our method to mock data in order to check whether our model is consistent, after which we use real data from CDF-S. As we have seen, the probabilistic approach allows us to obtain better characterizations of low count sources in the data as well as of our background normalization. Better constraints on background normalization will help us understand the sources of X-ray emission at high redshift, which would aid our understanding of early universe processes like galaxy and SMBH formation. Future work may involve cross-correlating X-ray data from CDF-S with optical and NIR surveys of the same region.

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